

THE ACTIVITIES OF THE INTERNAL AFFAIRS BODIES TO COUNTERACT THE COMMISSION OF CRIMES BY MINORS: ANALYSIS, PROBLEMS AND WAYS TO ELIMINATE THEM

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Abstract: The article considers in detail a number of targeted measures to counteract the commission of crimes by minors, which are one of the main activities of internal affairs bodies, the implementation of preventive measures against them and the protection of the rights of minors. In particular, early prevention of offenses among minors and youth; raising legal awareness and legal culture of minors; Large-scale systematic work on the protection of their rights was analyzed and opinions were expressed on further liberalization of criminal penalties imposed on them, prevention of juvenile crimes.

Keywords: minors, juvenile offenses, prevention of juvenile crimes, guarantee of the rights of minors.

To date, a number of targeted measures are being implemented in our republic to counteract the commission of crimes by minors, implement preventive measures and protect the rights of minors: early prevention of offenses among minors and youth; increase legal awareness and legal culture of minors; further liberalization of criminal penalties imposed against them, protection of their rights and freedoms; large-scale systematic work is being carried out.

In our country, developed on the principle of “From an action strategy to a development strategy”, the priority is to turn the principles of justice and the rule of law into the most important and necessary condition for development In order to fulfill the tasks in the development strategy of the New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026 and the state program for its implementation in the “Year of Glorification of Human Value and active Mahalla” it is necessary to conduct research on the study and prevention of juvenile delinquency, which indicates the need to study this topic.

Despite the ongoing work to ensure the rights and legitimate interests of the child, the number of crimes committed by minors remains significantly unchanged.

In particular, due to the insufficient organization of preventive measures by psychological inspectors for minors, together with preventive inspectors, mahalla activists and educational institutions, in 2022 the number of crimes committed by minors amounted to 2,404 (2,404/2262), an increase of 142, or 6.3 percent, compared to the same period last year.

The largest weight of crimes committed falls on the share of Ferghana – 67.7% (1st place), Tashkent city - 12.8% (2nd place), Tashkent –10.6% (3rd place), Namangan 7.1% (4th place) and Surkhandarya 5.9% regions.

Minors committed crimes such as 1,162 burglaries, 171 hooliganism, 137 frauds, 78 robberies, 74 grievous bodily harm, 42 rapes, 29 carjackings, 21 robberies and 10 murders.

In the context of the mahalla, the largest number of crimes among minors was registered in the mahalla “Oybek” of the city of Fergana - 17, in the mahalla “Sunbula” of the city of Kokand -13, in the mahalla “Uchkuprik” Uchkuduk district – 9, in the mahalla "Uchkuduk" of Chirchik city – 9, "Kamolot" of Chirchik city, "Wakf Chorsu" of Kokand city, "Yangiabad", "youth" of Ferghana city – 8, in the mahalla "Marifat" – 8, in the mahalla "Gulistan" of Termez city - 7, in the mahalla "Abad" of the city of Kokand - 5.

For example, on the night of March 2, 2022, a student of school No. 28, owned by MTB of the city of Kokand, born in 2007.t. citizen A., who was on the territory of the mahalla "Wakf Chorsu", broke a window in a retail store owned by B and stole electronic cigarettes for 300 thousand soums, a surveillance camera for 800 thousand soums and money for 300 thousand soums, causing material damage.

The causes of crimes, insufficient organization of preventive measures conducted by psychological inspectors for minors together with territorial inspectors of prevention, activists of the mahalla and the school administration, untimely participation of A minor in classes, participation in various sports or craft or similar target groups for meaningful leisure, as well as, as a result of neglect of parents or persons, their The basis for the commission of this crime is being created.

As a result of the proper and insufficient organization of preventive measures, legal propaganda among students of secondary schools conducted by psychological inspectors in the republic, 2,404 crimes committed during 2022 involved 2,089 schoolchildren compared to the same period last year.

Today, as a result of improper organization of preventive work with minors who are on preventive registration in the internal affairs bodies,

especially with previously convicted persons, they are allowed to re-commit crimes.

At the same time, the identification and registration of persons prone to committing offenses and crimes on the ground is sharply increasing, as well as the commission of crimes by certain categories of persons as a result of improper targeted preventive measures with them.

By Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 5050 dated April 2, 2021, positions of inspectors-psychologists for minors consisting of 2,000 staff units were introduced in district and city internal affairs bodies (currently these states have been transferred to the National Guard) and the places of their direct service in secondary educational institutions have been determined.

As a result of preventive measures carried out by psychological inspectors in 2022 with 89,098 students with difficult upbringing, 62,312 have changed for the better.

However, in Tashkent 5,203, Karakalpakstan 3,527, Andijan 3,511, Samarkand 2,445, Tashkent region 2,427 and Ferghana 2,357, preventive measures with students with difficult upbringing have not changed for the better due to improper organization.

The crimes committed by schoolchildren were analyzed in the context of schools for 3 years and attached to the senior staff of the internal affairs bodies in 2,155 schools whose students committed crimes. In respect of 29,583 parents who did not fulfill their obligations, administrative measures were taken in accordance with article 47 of the Administrative Code. 1,321 minors left without parental care were provided with social and legal assistance with placement in Social and Legal Assistance Centers.

Currently, in 6 months of 2024, 1113 of the minors placed in social and legal assistance centers were returned to their parents or persons replacing them, 4 were placed in a republican educational institution for boys, 6 - in family orphanages, 114 - in guardianship and guardianship authorities, 11 - in specialized educational institutions.

Based on the above, in order to further improve the social legal protection of minors, we considered it advisable to make the following proposals:

1) development of indicators to determine the mechanism for allocating budgetary funds to social and legal assistance centers for specific social purposes, as well as the effectiveness of their use;

2) expanding the practice of financing socially oriented projects by centers of social and legal assistance by allocating a clearly oriented social order from the form of a state grant;

3) an increase in the volume of implementation by the management bodies of the Ministry of Internal Affairs through the centers of social and legal assistance of the tasks and functions performed;

4) provision of social and legal assistance in the preparation of training programs and manuals on the discipline "Crime prevention" coverage of the activities of the centers, organization on its basis of continuous special training courses for representatives of government agencies and civil society institutions;

5) the introduction of the practice of organizing, together with civil society institutions, annual public hearings of the heads of social and legal assistance centers on issues related to ensuring the protection of the rights and legitimate interests of minors, the Public Chamber and the territorial Chambers of Communities;

6) support the specialization of social and legal assistance centers and stimulate the activities of the staff of this institution.

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